

JOSÉ IPARRAGUIRRE* – JAMES GOODWIN*

‘Winter mortality, temperature and influenza’ Revisiting Curwen and Devis after a quarter of a century

1. INTRODUCTION

Over 25 years ago Michael Curwen and Tim Devis (henceforth, C-D) published the paper “Winter mortality, temperature and influenza: has the relationship changed in recent years?” (Curwen and Devis, 1988), in which they reported that a 1°C decrease in winter temperature below its mean was associated with 8,000 excess winter deaths - that is, the difference between the number of deaths during the months of December to March (in the Northern hemisphere) and the average number of deaths occurring in the preceding August to November and the following April to July (ONS, 2012a). Given that this figure is now a quarter of a century old and that it is quoted (Collins, 1993; Langford and Bentham, 1995; Goodwin, 2000; Lawlor *et al.*, 2000; Donaldson, 2009) for lack of a more up to date estimate, this short paper replicates the original study with the most recently available data.

The issue of excess winter mortality transcends its purely statistical significance, however. An excess of deaths in the winter (EWD) over the remainder of the year was first reported in 1841 and though it has declined, it remains a public health priority (CMO, 2011). There have been 2,639,390 excess deaths over the last 61 winters in England and Wales alone - the average figure for the last ten years still runs at 26,652 per year (ONS, 2012a).

There is an established body of knowledge around the causes of EWD, including the underlying medical, physiological and sociological evidence as well as C-D’s regression data, which together may be termed ‘the grand model’. Establishing the trend and the factors associated with EWD according to the latest evidence is important not only to test the ‘grand model’ but also to provide insight which may be of use in dealing with an apparently intractable public health issue.

2. METHODS

C-D ran a regression analysis of excess winter mortality onto the number of registered influenza deaths in winter, the deviations of winter temperature from

* Age UK, London, United Kingdom.

Corresponding author: José Iparraguirre; e-mail: jose.iparraguirre@ageuk.org.uk

its mean, and a linear time trend. They used data between 1949/50 and 1984/85.

We have run the C-D's model with data between 1950/51 and 2011/12. The sources are: EWD (ONS, 2012a), Temperature (Met Office, 2012), and Influenza (and Pneumonia¹) deaths (ONS, 2011a, 2011b and 2012b).

The regression equation is:

$$EWD_t = \alpha \cdot I_t + \beta \cdot (\bar{T} - T_t) + \gamma \cdot Y_t + const$$

where,

EWD_t = excess winter mortality in year t

I_t = number of influenza deaths over the four winter months (i.e. December - March) in year t

T_t = average winter temperature (in °C) in year t

\bar{T} = mean of T_t

Y_t = linear trend (=1,2,...)

t = year (=1950,1951,...,1985).

These are their published results (no standard errors or statistical fit measures were reported):

$$EWD_t = 3.64 \cdot I_t + 7,750 \cdot (5.05 - T_t) - 534 \cdot Y_t + 51,870$$

Therefore, each registered winter influenza death was associated with just under 4 excess winter deaths, and a 1°C drop in winter temperature below its secular mean was associated with almost 8,000 excess winter deaths. Further, the number of excess winter deaths had been diminishing at a constant rate of 534 a year over the period.

3. RESULTS

Compared to C-D's findings, influenza ceased to be a significant factor, so we omitted this variable from the updated results below². This lack of statistical significance of influenza may reflect the low percentage of all-cause winter deaths attributable to influenza even among older people - around 4.3 per cent since 1999/2000 (Hardelid *et al.*, 2013) - and the varying effects on mortality of different strains even during pandemics (Donaldson and Keatinge, 2002; Green *et al.*, 2013).

¹ We used the 10th edition of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10), J09-J18 codes, and similarly for previous ICD editions. We included pneumonia to account for possible instability in the coding of influenza on its own.

² $EWD_t = 5,069 \cdot (4.66 - T_t) - 656 \cdot Y_t - 0.94 \cdot FLU_t + 65,977$
 (0.00) (0.00) (0.43) (0.00)
 (Adjusted R2: 0.53; F-statistic: 23.13 on 3 and 56 DF, p-value: 7.217e-10).

We ran a Breusch-Pagan test (Breusch and Pagan, 1979) and found evidence of heteroskedasticity in the regression residuals; hence we report corrected p-values using the White-Huber (White, 1980) correction (W-H heteroscedasticity-corrected p-values between parentheses):

$$EWD_t = 5,095. (4.66 - T_t) - 581. Y_t + 61,928$$

(0.0) (0.00) (0.00)

(Adjusted R2: 0.5465; F-statistic: 37.75 on 2 and 59 DF, p-value: 2.773e-11).

Therefore updating C-D’s original model with data up to 2011, we find that a 1°C drop in winter temperatures below their secular average is associated with about 5,100 deaths, and that on average excess winter mortality has been falling by 581 deaths a year over the period.

C-D did not control or factor in population growth over their period of study and neither did we. However, the number of excess winter deaths per person (i.e. the unadjusted excess winter mortality rate) presents, for each respective period, statistically the same trend and fluctuations than the series of excess winter mortality used in both C-D and this paper . Consequently, we do not consider it necessary to introduce any adjustment for population change.

4. DISCUSSION

On the basis of our new analysis, we may conclude that the evidence shows a downward trend in EWD, deaths falling on average by approximately 580 per year over a 60 year period and that this trend is accelerated compared to period studied by Curwen and Devis (1949/50 to 1984/85). We may also conclude, as did C-D, that temperature is still a main effect - with the caveat that at 5,100 deaths per degree Celsius variation, as opposed to 8,000 in the original regression, there is clearly some mitigation.

It is arguable that changes in meteorological conditions, behaviour, housing conditions, social policy and health care may be explanatory variables. Notwithstanding a re-consideration of the explanatory variables, ours are new and interesting statistical findings which challenge the wider scientific community to explain these trends and to state the public health implications.

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